

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Analysis of interactive manufacturing systems: Towards a performance-based assessment methodology

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Abstract

Current manufacturing systems are forced to meet the most dynamic market demands under sustainable factors. However, not only technical transformations will address the challenge but, to fully cover social needs, the analysis of the human role in highly interactive systems is still decisive, following a socially sustainable approach. To fully extract the most from both agents under a performance point of view, the main added value of agents in the work environment needs to be carefully analysed, captured, and boosted. The context shapes a specific operation or task, which consequently drives the final outcome according to individual necessities. Furthermore, a methodology that potentially helps a proper assessment of these performance-based interactions is still missing. The contribution focusses on the definition of a novel human-centric methodology under a holistic point of view to analyse performance-based interactions and to define appropriate indices and metrics that helps assessing the human-system interactions in the manufacturing domain. The methodology is applied in a case study to guide practitioners with its use.

1 | INTRODUCTION

In the manufacturing context, faster product changes and short life cycles are challenging current systems to meet the most dynamic market demands under sustainable aspects with implications in new service-oriented business models and smarter systems that must evolve, learn, and adapt on the fly. Challenges arise from the increasing unpredictability and complexity of future manufacturing systems which may be technologically overcome by the introduction of advanced models and algorithms, and by the use of the Internet to connect all these systems, that is, the digitisation of manufacturing processes. Thus, the mass customisation paradigm – or the one-of-a-kind production – may be embraced in a sustainable manner by means of the optimization of labours and use of resources, meaning the reinvention of production systems into Cyber-Physical Systems or Cyber-Physical Production Systems (CPPS) in manufacturing [1].

Furthermore, the adoption of these technological disruptions does not come alone: the responsible embracement of new roles for operators from a socially sustainable way must be

assured by the promotion of the well-being [2]. The conception of the Operator 4.0 [3] defines a skilled operator who performs collaborative works with machines and works aided by machines as needed by means of a collaborative symbiosis to achieve a common goal. The main objective of a true collaborative system is to capture the main added value of agents, defined as singular entities that interact in the work environment, with reference to individual activities and tasks rather than jobs. Agents' abilities are improved thanks to the creation of trust in a dynamic interaction-based relationship. In addition, employee work engagement must be guaranteed in a stable work environment, as opposed of job burnout, maintaining a positive fulfilling and an affective-motivational state of work-related well-being. Engaged employees pay attention and accept to put their energy on their work, which is essential to solve the most challenging problems.

In order to succeed with these value creation processes, researchers and developers need to understand how humans adapt to automation – or in last instance, to autonomous systems – both in the sense how they learn to rely on the manufacturing system as it develops more intelligent behaviours, and given that

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the system meets their expectations and satisfies their needs. Understanding the importance of the human factor is essential to design and develop new technology that closely interacts with humans, and whose functionality really leads to an increase in performance, safety, and efficiency avoiding misuse and/or disuse [4]. Interactions are created in situations in which an action is influenced by a mutual or reciprocal action or influence, along not only the physical environment but also the digital one. Under this definition, interactions that can be found in manufacturing environments may be classified as [5]:

- interactions in which humans influence/control the system, normally, with specific tasks and clear objectives;
- interactions in which machine's behaviour influences the human's belief and behaviour.

On the other hand, researchers and engineers commonly focus on designs that give priority to find solutions to technical issues, following a techno-centred approach that favours the task allocation only to automated systems and giving to the human the role of supervision to determine the objectives, to tune the parameters, constraints, and rules. Even the adoption of human-in-the-loop (HitL) approaches can be interpreted more as a way of keeping humans in the 'decisional/responsibility loop' but not in the 'control loop', since the human operator is excluded from the decisions made by the control system [6]. In addition, it is often assumed that the over-estimated ability of the human operator – who behaves perfectly when desired and within appropriate response times as well as reacts perfectly in the face of unexpected situations – will allow to flawlessly supervise and handle all the unforeseen situations on the fly. In contrast, in a human-centred approach, the human operator must be involved in the dynamics of the construction of decisions, being aware of the system runtime and an important decisional part of what would be the right rule or parameter to tune while keeping an appropriate balance of the workload. What is more, when a robot or a manufacturing system is compared to a human under a social context, robots or systems always loose, and as consequence, the collaboration is drastically affected due to the lack of acceptance or reliability on that technology or system, which directly drives to a general performance detriment. The correct understanding of this fact gains even more importance if the sources of complexity and unpredictability of the systems' responses are considered [7]. In these highly interactive environments where a *user-centric* design is not enough, a *human-centric* design assures a sustainable introduction of the socio-technical aspects along the whole system's life cycle, aiming at a mutual synchronization and understanding of operations and tasks to meet common manufacturing goals, built around a shared cognition [8] and cognitive attitudes as mutual reliability and trust.

Given the huge challenges that new manufacturing systems have ahead, the issue of designing proper manufacturing systems is still widely investigated, yet considering that human conduct models and cognitive mechanisms are not fully known. In this sense, the Research through Design (RtD)

[9, 10] model may help the research community to engage with hurtful problems that cannot be easily solved through science and engineering methods as well as with gaps in behavioural theory and complex behaviours. The iterative nature of the concept potentially feeds new research opportunities by the creation of reflecting points where the extraction of new theories is built or modification of previous ones are conducted.

Considering all aforementioned socio-technical issues, there exists a practical necessity to establish a validated and repeatable holistic method to evaluate and monitor interactions, taking into account the multiple nature of factors affecting performance. Moreover, it is also of high importance to utilise appropriate performance metrics, feasible to be measured, sensitive to and that can effectively capture critical operator states and their influences on human-machine interactions [11]. These metrics not only will help understanding current performance of collaborative systems, but also serve as a guidance on how the system must evolve or how new developments must be lined up considering practical necessities, for instance, following the RtD method. From an operational point of view, validated metrics of collaborative performance can be traced to specific operators' skills and behaviours due to social diversity, allowing the system to adapt to those circumstances, hence being flexible and adaptable, not only considering job places, but at low-level actions or tasks.

In summary, this work aims at the definition of a methodology to help setting different indicators and metrics for performance-based interaction assessment by the analysis of the importance of the interactions among agents within a manufacturing ecosystem. The nature of collaborative interactions will be affected by the introduction of new CPPS technologies since systems may show new autonomous functions with close physical interactions. The methodology followed for the literature search is described in Section 1.1. Section 2 presents the theories behind human-machine interactions by analysing different factors that are directly correlated with performance. For a clearer understanding, these factors have been divided in different dimensions: (i) user factors, (ii) machine factors, (iii) collaborative factors, and (iv) manufacturing factors. Section 3 introduces the proposed model and methodology to extract main indicators and metrics. The application of the methodology in real use cases is presented in Section 4. Lastly, the document finishes with main conclusions and remarks in Section 5.

1.1 | Literature search methodology

In this work, the most relevant individual factors affecting performance are considered, pointing to the feasibility of measuring each of the interactive factor and main troubles or issues. Hence, this section presents the methodology followed during the literature research and main findings that may affect the approach, such as trends in research efforts on specific areas. Due to the multiple nature of the analysed factors, different keywords have been used in order to carry out a

comprehensive analysis of the state of the art of literature. Two different analyses have been conducted: the first looking for trends in manufacturing and human-machine interactions, and a second that aims at stressing the last efforts done in measurement methods. The Scopus database has been used and publications have been classified as before and after the year 2015. Articles published before 2015 were ranked according to citations to obtain relevant publications including important research concepts, while articles published after 2015 were filtered manually seeking for latest research works. Table 1 shows the number of publications related by field.

An initial search was performed to analyse the main research trends in the manufacturing context (see Table 2). Despite equipment performance and safety concerns are significantly high in comparison to other concepts related to psychological states of the operators, situational awareness and engagement are still considerably low and are still not a trend in the manufacturing context, which may also be extracted from Figure 1.

Publications regarding safety and general machine performance show a positive trend along last years, showing their attraction in a manufacturing context. As pointed previously, the inclusion of more psychological concepts in manufacturing environments is still very low (see Figure 2). Figure 1 shows publications of specific keywords, which indicates a clear tendency of safety concerns in manufacturing environments.

In a general context, last research works show a huge trend in measuring performance of equipment but also safety measurements –209,914 and 35,834 publications, respectively,

since 2015. The number of publications, including trust as a keyword and related to measurement methods, shows a slight positive trend as well as workload measurements and situational awareness (see Figure 3). It is worth to note that performance and equipment keywords have been removed from Figure 3 to better show trends in concepts with lower numbers.

FIGURE 1 Number of publications per year with reference to the manufacturing context (dated until the second semester 2021)

Keywords	Publications before 2015	After 2015
Human-machine interactions	18,127	18,302
Human factors + manufacturing	30,729	48,793
Machine performance + manufacturing	8,289	6,192
Safety and ergonomics + manufacturing	9,980	7,040
Human factors + measurement	201,485	175,326
Machine performance + measurement	135,590	209,914
Safety and ergonomics + measurement	58,768	35,834

TABLE 1 Number of publications by field (dated until second semester 2021)

Keywords	Publications before 2015	After 2015
Workload + manufacturing	1,235	749
Trust + manufacturing	992	797
Situational awareness + manufacturing	45	70
Reliance + manufacturing	2,588	2,172
Robot performance + manufacturing	1,471	1,415
Machine performance + manufacturing	8,289	6,192
Safety + manufacturing	8,226	5,871
Ergonomics + manufacturing	1,754	1,169

TABLE 2 Number of publications by keywords used during the initial literature search (dated until the second semester 2021)

FIGURE 2 Number of publications per year and field with reference to manufacturing context (dated until the second semester 2021)

FIGURE 3 Number of publications per year with reference to measurement concepts (dated until the second semester 2021). Publication values regarding *machine performance measurement* and *safety measurements* have been removed for better clarity

2 | TAXONOMY OF INTERACTIONS

In the manufacturing context, interactions are continuously exchanged between involved agents and may even be performed simultaneously at different levels [12]. These levels are shaped around agents' behaviours and the context in which single tasks or operations are performed.

The ability to avoid problems remains on the potential to understand what is happening now (what the collaborator is doing) and to predict what will happen (or what the collaborator will do) [13].

Circumstances or situational characteristics that shape an interaction in terms of environmental definition, objectives, causes, effects, consequences, or results define the context. Therefore, agents' function or position in a particular situation is defined according to individual purposes or objectives. In addition, the context plays a major role to set interactions as defined by the engagement of operators with the specific tasks [14]. The context is classified as: *purely social* when no form of task is involved, *competitive*, *informative*, *educative*, *negotiation*, *guide-and-follow*, and *collaborative*. A common approach to set the level of interactions is (see Figure 4): (i) *basic interaction or coexistence*, (ii) *synchronization*, (iii) *cooperation*, and (iv) *collaboration*.

The main dimensions affecting interactions can be classified as follows (see Figure 5): (i) user, (ii) machine, (iii) collaborative, and (iv) production-related ones.

2.1 | User-related factors

User's factors affecting productivity are directly related to the engagement as a consequence of personal experience. The inherent energy and focus in work engagement allow users to bring their full potential, thus improving performance. Such a subjective state at an operational level may be mainly driven by analysing job stress caused by high job demands and low job control [15–17].

Taken the initial concept from the aviation field, situation awareness (SA) is the ability to perceive and comprehend what is happening around the main agent and the ability to predict what will happen in future [11]. Situation awareness is the active cognitive representation of the functional state with reference to the achievement of an objective in the context of a specific task and is driven by (i) the supply of attentional resources, (ii) demands on attentional resources, and (iii) the operator's understanding of the task. It results in internal changes of mental models and has a strong effect in the decision-making process that may result in an improvement of performance and definitely is critical for minimising errors.

Among others, the situation awareness rating technique [18] evaluates subjective measurements of situational awareness by operators and measures attentional supply, attentional demand, and understanding of the task. The crew awareness rating technique is based on group questionnaires according to the resources available during different functional steps, such as perception, comprehension, projection, and integration of all previous resources. In contrast, the situational awareness behaviourally anchored rating scale assesses SA by an external observer to evaluate behaviours.

As a critical human factor, operators' fatigue or stress may have a severe influence in productivity and safety in multiple industrial domains. Indeed fatigue, as a characteristic with a direct consequence of long-term effort – physical or mental – has a close correlation with workload allocation (see Section 2.3 for workload balance). Thus, it is of high importance to its appropriate balance according to individual preferences in the most natural manner while preserving user

FIGURE 4 Classification of interaction levels. Adapted from [12]

FIGURE 5 Dimensions in a collaborative manufacturing ecosystem

situational awareness [19]. Although issues regarding operator fatigue are largely known, cognitive fatigue is rarely considered in practice during the design and implementation phases of highly collaborative systems [11].

Theories of cognitive or mental workload postulate that the amount of resources (relative to capacity) required to cope with a task load, which can be dynamically allocated and decrease over time, has distinct time-dynamic components [20]. Hence, it is confirmed that workload influences negative performance for most of the people and could potentially be monitored in order to adjust task demands [21], but the complexity of the association between workload and performance obligates to further research regarding its effects – between-person effects, for example, in different resources capacity, and within-person relations. According to this resource theory, the threaded cognition assumes that cognition keeps an active set of task goals that results in threads of processing across a set of available resources during multi-tasking [22]. Threads can arise from conflicts when multiple tasks require the same peripheral resource or when multiple tasks require attention from the central procedural resource. Furthermore, threaded recognition initially relies on memorised instructions but transforms a skill to a more highly procedural process through learning.

The multiple resource model architecture defines the concept of mental workload with high relevance to its source

and performance breakdowns related to task overload [20, 23]. It consists of demand, resource overlap, and allocation policy avoiding frustration in the workplace while raising comfort. Although mental workload relates mostly to the demand, the model is described by (i) *Work process*, which relates to different stages, such as (i) perception, (ii) (re) cognition, and (iii) responding; *perceptual modalities*, which analyse sensory mechanisms that normally include visual, auditory, and tactile resources; *processing codes*, related to cognitive systems mainly involved with spatial and verbal comprehension.

Based on these resource models, many efforts focus on measuring and mapping a unit change in how the operator is performing to a unit change in resource allocation [24, 25]. The capacity coefficient measures the change in performance – how well the operator performs according to the response time – as the number of task-relevant information sources increases by comparison of the observed performance to predicted performance – or cognitive model, depending of the number or information sources available. As drawbacks, it assumes unlimited capacity, independent, and parallel processing of information sources.

The well-known NASA task load index (TLX or NASA TLX) questionnaire self-reports operators' workload while performing tasks by measuring six subscales: (i) *mental demand*, (ii) *physical demand*, (iii) *temporal demand*, (iv) *performance*, (v) *effort*, and (vi) *frustration*. Other instruments for measuring workload are:

- the *modified Cooper-Harper scale*, developed in 1969 for aircraft handling;
- the *subjective workload assessment technique*: a two-phased method developed in 1988 that includes a scale development phase based on conjoint measurement and non-metric scaling, and an event scoring phase; and

- the *workload profile* that includes the multidimensional procedure and information of workload.

The Detection Response Task (DRT, ISO17488:2016) [26] methodology is used to objectively assess the attentional effects of cognitive workload on attention for secondary tasks involving interaction with visual-manual, voice-based, or haptic interfaces and evaluates real-time fluctuations in workload that can be applied in many real-world tasks [21]. The nonparametric multitasking throughput [27] uses the full function of performance to compute and combine multitask efficiency across all tasks. This metric estimates the degree to which cognitive processes are hampered, improved, or stay invariant when multitasking, that is, shows quantitative and categorically results as (i) resources are split between tasks and limit the throughput (negative value); (ii) appropriate, then the throughput is unlimited (value equal to zero); or (iii) resources exceed the demand and efficiency improves (super throughput or positive value).

2.2 | Machine-related factors

This dimension includes indicators exclusively applicable to the manufacturing equipment. The performance of manufacturing machines is specific due to the multiple domains and operations to be performed, and so their use. Numerous standards and directives have been developed at national and international levels to cover performance assessment of the equipment, which can be looked up for specific guidance. For example, the ISO230 standard covers general machine tools' accuracy and repeatability tests as well as uncertainty measurement methods; guidance for testing accuracy and repeatability of machining centres, including the evaluation operational times during tool changes, are defined in the ISO10791; the ISO13041 sets conditions for numerical controlled machines considering position repeatability and accuracy, speeds and interpolations of axes. Finally, the ISO9283 defines performance criteria and test methods for robotic manipulators.

It establishes basic definitions, concepts, and methods to correctly measure the performance of industrial manipulators. Performance indices can be classified in [28] (i) local or global – posture dependent or independent, (ii) kinematic or dynamic, and (iii) intrinsic or extrinsic to the task or operation. In general, two challenges arise in terms of performance: (i) the proximity to low performance configurations or kinematic singularities, and (ii) the effective use of the workspace by optimising operation-oriented criteria. For example, the main performance indices for manipulators are [28, 29]:

- *Joint performance indices* are normally local and exclusive of each joint, such as the joint velocity measurement, the joint mid-range proximity, or the service angle and service sphere.
- *Manipulability indices* evaluate mathematically the proximity to a manipulator singularity or the ill-conditioning in the workspace, highlighting the use of the global manipulability, the dynamic manipulability, which quantifies the

manipulating ability of a robot's end-effector with consideration of its arm dynamics, or the minimum singular value, which represents the direction in which it is most difficult for the manipulator's end-effector to move, ignoring all other directions, and is better indicator of closeness to singularities.

- *Redundancy indices* measure the ability for a manipulator to change its configuration with a fixed end-effector. Redundant manipulators can avoid kinematic singularities, improve dexterity and therefore avoid obstacle collisions easier, and are fault tolerant.
- *Isotropy and task-related* indices evaluate the manipulator's ellipsoid isotropy. The layout conditioning index may also help evaluating how appropriate the manipulator's design is for a specific task but, in general, the task-dependent performance index and the robot task-conformance index assess manipulator's capabilities to perform operations in a highly task-changing environment. Other common local metrics are accuracy and repeatability measurements [29] and are defined following Gaussian distributions – normal distribution, non-Gaussian distribution, or a total anisotropy repeatability.

2.3 | Collaboration-related factors

As previously exposed, user workload is a major factor affecting user's productivity in conjunction with technological developments. Consequently, the workload balance in a natural manner is almost compulsory according to human factors. However, a proper workload balance will only be achieved if and only if both agents can exchange the responsibility of actions to construct upon a common goal or objective. To some limitation, they must build upon a sense of mutual trust, always keeping that both agents' behaviour may seriously affect safety and ergonomic aspects, which also contribute to this sense of reliance. Current works in the collaborative robotics field lead the majority of improvements, where very close physical interactions more commonly occur in the manufacturing domain.

Trust is defined as a cognitive attitude, which includes the belief that the collaborator – human or system – will perform as expected and can – within the limits of its/his/her abilities or the designer's intentions – be relied on to achieve the design goals or objectives [5]. As a dynamic state, collaborator's limitations are defined according to its/his/her base knowledge or experiences along time, that is, learning processes. The notion of trust involves a bidirectional feedback between involved agents based on the vulnerability of the trustor to the trustee in circumstances of risk and uncertainty, and as a consequence, an improper calibration of trust produces system disuse, misuse – then, performance decrements – and can cause accidents. In essence, higher trust is associated with higher reliability [30, 31]. Moreover, the importance trust has over a collaborative scenario not only comes from its consequences but also from the complexity of the different factors affecting it, which can be classified as [30]:

- *Human-related*, including ability-based (attentional capacity, expertise and experience, workload, or situational awareness) and personal characteristics (demographics, personality traits, attitudes towards robots, comfort, self-confidence, or propensity).
- *Robot-related*, including performance-based factors (behaviour, dependability, reliability, predictability, or transparency) and attribute-based (proximity, personality, adaptability, robot type, or anthropomorphism).
- *Environmental*, considering team collaboration (in-group membership, culture, and shared mental models) and tasking (type, complexity, multi-tasking requirement, and physical environment).

In practice, operator's trust is normally evaluated by using questionnaires but suffer from intrusiveness that can perturbate the situation and hidden real beliefs. Automatic reports through psychometric instruments provide the most direct measurements by using sensors and models to estimate real values [32]. However, during real demonstrations and tests, trust levels behave in a very dynamical manner, not reaching steady-state failing in the estimation. Another limitation considers its long-term changing nature since trust is affected by familiarity process as increasing user familiarity with the system decreases the rate of trust change [30]. These dynamics are especially critical during the very beginning of the interaction when there is no information from past experiences.

On the other hand, collaborative environments should follow very strict standards and regulations. Safety mechanisms must meet the corresponding industrial standards, which are built in hierarchical levels [33]:

- *Laws and directives* for safety requirements as a general machinery: European Machinery Directive 2006/42/EC.
- *Type A standards* for basic safety: Functional safety by IEC62508, risk assessment by ISO12100, and safety devices and active controls ISO12100.
- *Type B standards* for specific applications: Manufacturing applications by ISO11161:2007.
- *Type C standards* for collaborative robots as products: Robotic cells by ISO10218-2 and robot systems by ISO20218, robots and Human-Robot Collaboration by ISO10218-1, and for speed limits by ISO15066.

However, not only due to regulations, operators must have a feeling of safety when interacting with manufacturing systems, especially in those cases in which there exists a very close collaboration and interaction with high proximity.

Due to the multidisciplinary – and complex – nature of new manufacturing systems and their responses under unpredictable circumstances, current safety measures are studied to be implemented during different phases of the systems' life cycle [7]: (i) *design process* and (ii) *operational phase*. In this context, the IEC61508 and IEC62508 establish general management rules to achieve adequate safety, although the second focusses more on the human-machine interface. In this context, some of the safety assurance methods are [7]:

- i) *Hazard identification*. Defines all scenarios or sequences of events that can result in a hazard. Since this work deals with collaborative systems, it is of huge significance to perform a *collaborative assessment*; that is, the analysis of collaborative hazards. For instance, the *Human Reliability Analysis* identifies and assesses hazards as a consequence of the human action coming from different sources and then using different methods: *first-generation methods* from the task implemented and the impact of the environment; *second-generation methods*, using the context, the cognitive operations, and commissioning errors; and *third-generation methods* based on simulations and virtual environments.
- ii) *Risk assessment*. Analytical method to identify and assess risks in complex technological systems for the purpose of improving their safety and performance in a cost-effective process.
- iii) *Verification and validation*. These methods define processes to validate hardware and software entities from a general point of view to avoid faults in those devices that can result in non-expected functions or operations.

In addition, ergonomics studies refer to improvements in work conditions in industry to avoid work-related musculoskeletal disorders and increase operators' comfort in the workplace. Some gestures may affect the performance of the system by directly affecting the human state. In this sense, the ISO9241 establishes ergonomic requirements in workplaces, including aspects of usability – hardware, software, and processes – and it is currently divided in:

- 100 series: Software ergonomics.
- 200 series: Human system interaction processes.
- 300 series: Displays and display-related hardware.
- 400 series: Physical input devices – ergonomics.
- 500 series: Workplace ergonomics.
- 600 series: Environment ergonomics.
- 700 series: Application domains – Control rooms.
- 900 series: Tactile and haptic interactions.

Real-time recognition tools can be used to score non-ergonomic postures in industrial tasks, such as the rapid upper limb assessment or the rapid entire body assessment. These methods rely on direct observations using trackers [34] or predictions of movements using non-intrusive observations and probabilistic surrogate models [35, 36] or machine learning techniques [37, 38], which often require huge amounts of datasets to be trained directly from demonstrations.

It is important to highlight that, considering the new paradigm in smart production systems, which are expected to adapt and evolve, some of the current safety methods are still applied in a static manner, that is, only used during design and deployment phases and hence the necessity to include the operational phase due to the dynamic changing nature of new production systems. For example, dynamic risk assessment mechanisms that may analyse and compare the nature of tasks or single operations with wrong utilization of tools or behaviours.

2.4 | Production-related factors

All production environments seek for maximising productivity improving the value creation processes by reducing costs, misuse of materials and maximising quality aspects of all activities. However, these top-level indicators are decomposed in lower-level metrics that can be measured at a shopfloor level in discrete and continuous production lines [39, 40]. These metrics enable tracking the performance and fault or problem detection before becoming critical by identifying trends relative to certain operational objectives.

The ISO 22400 focuses on metrics calculated using data from the control domain and to provide both the enterprise (high level) domain and the manufacturing operation management (MOM, intermediate level) domain with decision support information to manage the enterprise (see Figure 6). Key performance indicators (KPIs) [40–42] must ensure their usefulness in achieving production goals at the operational level, thus created following certain criteria, such as *aligned, valid and timely, trackable and predictive, quantifiable and accurate, comparable, actionable, standardised and documented*.

The identification and selection of KPIs in the production domain cover the following steps:

- i) Identification of operations and elements of operations to be evaluated;
- ii) Objectives to be realized with the use of performance indicators are determined;
- iii) Description of operational actions when using performance indicators to realize expectations or goals;
- iv) Definition of assessment criteria and associated measurements for performance indicators;
- v) Selection of KPIs;
- vi) Assessment of performance versus objectives with the KPIs obtained

In general, the production rate indicates the number of pieces produced per time unit. It can be measured considering the cycle times for single operations, including the time that takes the operation process itself, the handling and tooling process. The maximum number of product unities that can be

FIGURE 6 Functional manufacturing hierarchy. Adapted from [43]

manufactured in a period of time defines the production capacity or production limit. More individually, the production rate of a specific machine can be established as well. Quality of production environments is widely studied but some common indicators are acceptance ratios, production yield (products not compliant with internal standards), reject ratio (returns from client), or supplier incoming quality. Other metrics help understanding behaviours of production lines and include the work in progress, downtime-assess reliability-, and change cycle times or changeovers-time that takes to implement modifications.

3 | PERFORMANCE-BASED ASSESSMENT APPROACH

A tentative model to set appropriate performance indicators is discussed. A set of methodological steps are presented as well to help industrial practitioners to use and deploy proper metrics in real-case scenarios.

The collaborative model, as shown in Figure 7, extends the dimensions to cover important aspects and to guide on KPI's assessment.

The model proposes *trust and reliability* as the main pillar due to their implications on creating collaboration and balanced interactions. It is a bidirectional dimension: it is built by the operator's *engagement* as well as the machine *behaviour and characteristics*, while having implications on both sides as well. Trust and reliability measurements are a reflection of workload balance and a result of the feeling of safety and comfort in the work environment. Two group of factors can be set according to the *machine* dimension: extrinsic or task-related, and intrinsic or inherent to the machine. They define machine's performance according to own characteristics and even emerging behaviours not initially programed. Factors related to the *user* analyse the engagement through the situational awareness. Similarly, *safety* and *ergonomics* factors are of huge importance to create reliable interactions under the user perception. In this dimension, collaborative assessment methods based on the context and cognitive operations are of huge importance to detect and prevent faults, although simulation methods are expected to be more effective in CPPS to detect and analyse the impact in highly dynamic environments. *Performance* and output *quality* of the production system are then established as a consequence of all previous dimensions and built around collaborative objectives in tasks, merging the results of both agents – that is, machine and user.

3.1 | Assessment methodology

The appropriate selection of indices and metrics requires the use of a methodology. For that purpose, guidelines to set indicators should follow these steps (see Figure 8):

1. *Context*: Set context and tasks, including operations performed by users, machines, and both. The first step

FIGURE 7 Taxonomy model of different measurement aspects of a collaborative environment

FIGURE 8 Performance-based assessment methodology to evaluate a collaborative manufacturing environment

requires the analysis and decomposition of jobs in specific tasks and operations, according to the functional hierarchy of the manufacturing system. Each task may be

characterised by the use of specific tools, different interaction levels, and roles. Furthermore, specific user/machine configurations, skills, or abilities might also be identified during this step in order to distinguish operations performed by users, machines, and with assistance of both, which may also contribute to a better design of the manufacturing system.

2. *Safety and ergonomics*: Identify hazards and perform the risk and collaborative assessment, any possible intrusions or perturbations from the environment should be considered. Considering each one of the tasks identified in the previous step, it is highly recommended to perform a hazard and risk assessment, especially considering the collaborative nature. Possible ergonomic issues may arise here.
3. *Indices and metrics*: List indices and metrics under all dimensions. This step considers the proposed model to study required indices in order to properly identify those indices that affect performance. Inputs to this step are the tasks to be performed, the agent involved (personnel or machine), the role and main restrictions or limitations. Each dimension (user, machine, collaboration, and production) may be studied independently to help with the holistic assessment.

4. *Transitory nature*: Consider temporal variations at short- and long-term identifying the dimensions and metrics affected. This last step covers the identification of those indices and metrics that may vary along time. The whole life cycle of the production ecosystem must be considered here from the design phase to the exploitation.

Furthermore, new contexts or roles might also emerge as a consequence of processes of trivial improvements related to autonomous behaviours or when operators get use to the

system. Due to both factors, the number of indices might start growing exponentially, although the systematic assessment in an iterative manner might help organising indices and relations.

3.2 | Summary of indicators

Considering the collaborative model and all different dimensions, indicators, and metrics can be set. A summary of principal indicators is presented in Table 3.

TABLE 3 Use case analysis of indicators

Factors		Metrics	Description	Refs.
User	Workload	Mental or cognitive demand	Mental effort the operator is required to perform according to the operations or tasks	[20, 22, 23, 26, 27]
		Physical demand	Physical effort the operator is required to perform according to the operations or tasks	[22]
	Situational awareness	Attention	Level of perception of the operation and surroundings	[11, 18]
	Engagement	Motivation/Frustration	Level of comfort or discomfort the user experiences performing operations or tasks	[15–27]
Machine	Intrinsic	Joint velocity and mid-range proximity	Quantification of local characteristics of manipulators' joints	[28]
		Dynamic and relative manipulability	Indicator of the manipulator's ability to generate an accurate trajectory – and forces – in a determined direction	[28]
		MSV and condition number	Indicate direction in which it is most difficult for the manipulator's end-effector to move (illcondition)	[28]
		Accuracy and repeatability	Values of end-effector precision	[28, 29]
	Extrinsic	Layout conditioning index	Quantification of the manipulator design to be appropriate for a specific task	[28]
		Task dependent performance	Indicate manipulator's ability to meet force requirements on a determined direction for a specific task	[28]
		Workload	Effort the system performs according to the number of operations or tasks that is performing	[8, 22]
Collaboration	Reliance and trustworthiness	Team expertise	Definition of the level of technical qualification	[5, 30–32]
		Workload balance	Workload ratio between involved agents	[19]
	Safety	Hazards and risks	Quantity of hazards and risks of different levels presented during the operation	[7]
		Proximity	Proximity monitoring between agents of the operations	[34–36]
		Usability complaints	Number of complaints regarding usability of the system	[15, 16]
Ergonomics	Non-ergonomic postures	Count of non-ergonomic postures	[34–38]	
Production	Performance	Cycle time	Total time to produce an outcome unit	[40–42]
		Task capacity	Maximum capacity of the production in a fixed time	[40–42]
		WIP	Quantity of outcome units in the system	[40–42]
		Downtimes	Number of stops as a consequence of faults	[40–42]
		Average changeover time	Time accounted for the last change in production	[40–42]
	Quality	Accepted/rejected products	Non-favourable outcome units according to requirements	[40–42]
Input quality		Non-favourable input units according to requirements (supply)	[40, 42]	

Each factor belongs to a dimension (i.e. collaboration, machine, user, and production); therefore, the relations and implications might be easily defined according to the aforementioned model description. The *user* dimension covers main metrics that may indicate operator's state; for example, cognitive, and physical demands, attention, or operator's comfort level. The deployment of a collaborative robotic system has been considered for the analysis of the indicators related to the *machine* dimension. In case of using other equipment, readers may refer to Section 2.2 in order to individualise each factor. Consequently, intrinsic and extrinsic factors may be set. The *collaborative* dimension sets trust and reliability as main factors, which might be assessed using metrics as expertise evaluation or workload balance in addition to safety and ergonomic factors. General production factors are established as the outcome of all previous factors, therefore affecting performance and quality metrics.

4 | CASE STUDY ANALYSIS

This section proposes a brief analysis of a user case that is based on an industrial scenario taken from the COVR toolkit [46, 47]. This toolkit helps at different stages of a collaborative robot – cobot – implementation by the presentation of a case study and a solution towards the safe physical interaction. The following analysis aims at analysing how and where to extract principal indicators in a real collaborative environment.

The chosen case study focusses on the continuous and accurate tracking of operators that work closely with collaborative robots, avoiding the use of intrusive sensors. Main technical challenges arise from the necessity of combining heterogeneous data from different sensor technologies aiming at device-free monitoring as well as the use of advance analytical tools [44, 45] (see Figure 9).

Machine factors might be directly or indirectly extracted from the controller and calculated [28] for the assessment. Important intrinsic indices include joint velocity and mid-range proximity, dynamic and relative manipulability, or the condition number. Accuracy and repeatability values might be assessed by regularly performing specific calibration tasks. Layout conditioning index and task performance may be calculated

during the task definition phase, while the workload should be constantly monitored since may vary according to different factors, for example, the level of collaboration or production demand.

The main *production* indices will depend on the deployment context as well, but cycle time, task capacity, downtimes monitoring, changeover times, and quality metrics are noteworthy indicators of overall production status.

Relative to *collaborative* factors, hazards and risks indices, and the evaluation of non-ergonomic postures are of high importance. In the long term, the number of complains may serve as a metric to assess usability of the system. Furthermore, the nature of the solution may increase positively workload balance by improving autonomous decision-making. However, the situational awareness – and most of the *user* factors – may be drastically affected if the operator is not completely conscious of the decisions taken by the controller of robots' behaviour nor future actions, therefore seriously affecting performance. Hence, not only physical demand metrics are of huge importance to correctly balance workload, but cognitive demands and attention metrics as well. This situation might even be more important in case of possible errors due to malfunctions. For this reason, it is highly recommended its deployment in conjunction with an active verification and validation method that continuously informs operators about the correct execution of the system and an active monitoring system sensitive to operator's trust dynamics. Safety and collaborative indices are crucial since they may better explain drastic changes in performance when deployed in real work environments.

In summary, this case represents one critical example where the correct deployment may be decisive in the final performance of the manufacturing system and thus the importance of an appropriate set of assessment indicators.

5 | CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a novel human-centric methodology based on a holistic model to analyse performance-based interactions of manufacturing systems while considering their collaborative nature. The approach is based on different dimensions and clearly classifies and analyses the most appropriate indicators

FIGURE 9 Description of the use-case scenario. From [44, 45]

and metrics by understanding their effect, relation with the performance of the system, and feasibility of measurements. The application of this model not only assists practitioners during the design phase but to continuously evaluate the needs by establishing a set of indicators that can evolve along the life cycle of the system.

The first step of the methodology focusses on the analysis of the context as a significant consideration since it primarily sets the scope of the study. Due to its importance, collaborative metrics and indicators should be established in parallel to the design of tasks and operations. The level of interactions and all interactive characteristics should be studied first. However, interactions may change and evolve as a consequence of emerging behaviours; then, the necessity reiteratedly evaluates them over time and during the operational phase as well.

Results of the literature analysis stress the variety of factors affecting collaborative interactions. Thus, metrics have been classified in different dimensions, that is, user, machine, collaboration, and production. According to the findings in literature, reliability and trust are the main pillars of the collaboration due to their influence in building a solid team and, consequently, affecting overall performance. The interaction should boost operator's situational awareness as another key factor as well as trust and reliability as a core of the interaction, rarely considered in current assessment methods. Their proper evaluation may potentially avoid errors or failures while increasing the performance. A healthy working environment assures the operator engagement bringing their full potential and improving performance. An improper assessment can result in unsafe situations and should be monitored through the use of these validated indicators. Biometric measurements lack on repeatability and precision, while mental models might help in understanding its dynamics, which can be deployed in the core of new CPPS. However, as more autonomous characteristics and functionalities will become a reality, the concepts of meaningful human control, accountability, and responsibility will gain traction on practical implementations to keep high levels of reliability in control frameworks, enabled by accurate indicators and metrics.

As can be seen in the study case, the mix of physical and virtual tools and technologies deployed in production environments will definitely affect interactions and will boost performance in different manufacturing levels. But these tools should be wisely selected and balanced according to individual features and operations, correctly assessed using appropriate indices.

In conclusion, new standardized procedures and methods for the assessment of collaborative scenarios are to be found; yet the proposed methodology sets an initial guideline to individually study each factor and aids at setting different indicators to help understanding performance-based interactions. Future stages of the research work will cover a more in deep use in real interactive scenarios and its practical validation. The performance of the framework will be further studied and presented by using numerical methods.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Jose Antonio Mulet alberola: Conceptualization, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing. **Irene Fassi:** Supervision, writing – review and editing.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

All authors declared no relevant conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

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